

QUESTIONNAIRE regarding euthanasia of palliative patients

Euthanasia - ending a person's life in a quick and painless way - in some countries of the world is the choice of a patient with an incurable disease that causes severe pain and suffering. The survey is conducted among palliative patients, their relatives, medical and social workers, priests who provide assistance to palliative patients and/or their relatives (caregivers), among scientists of Ukraine studying the issue of palliative care organization. Answers for an adult palliative patient can be provided by a relative, guardian, doctor or social worker. Please answer the following questions anonymously, write the answer or underline the required option:

Your gender*

Man

Woman

Other

Your age (in full years)* _____

I am answering the questions of this questionnaire for the first time *

- Yes - please continue to answer

- No - please make sure you are correcting previous answers and not re-answering

you *

- an adult (adult) palliative patient and answer the questions yourself

- a relative (guardian) of a palliative patient and answer the questions on your own behalf

- the relative (guardian) of the palliative patient, on whose behalf you are answering the question

- a doctor treating palliative patients

- a nurse who treats palliative patients

- a social worker who provides services to palliative patients (takes care of)

- a priest who provides spiritual support to palliative patients

- a volunteer who provides support to palliative patients (caregiver)

- a scientist studying issues of palliative and hospice care

- other _____

Are you a religious person? *

Yes

No

*Mandatory questions

Answer if you are an adult palliative patient. **What is your palliative diagnosis?**

Answer if you are an adult palliative patient. **Do you experience frequent unbearable pain?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are an adult palliative patient. **Have you ever thought about suicide?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are an adult palliative patient. **Where do you undergo treatment?**

Home

In the hospice

In a regular hospital

In a home for the elderly

Other _____

Answer if you are a relative (guardian) of a palliative patient. **Where does the treatment take place?**

In the hospice

In a hospital where other (non-palliative) patients are also treated

Home

Answer if you are a relative (guardian) of a palliative patient. **Have you ever thought about the need for euthanasia for your palliative patient?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a relative (guardian) of a palliative patient and speak on his behalf (record his answer).

What is the patient's palliative diagnosis?

*Mandatory questions

Answer if you are a relative (guardian) of a palliative patient and speak on his behalf (record his answer). **Has the patient ever had suicidal thoughts?**

Yes

No

The patient does not want to answer this question

Answer if you are a relative (guardian) of a palliative patient and speak on his behalf (record his answer). **Would the patient like to have the possibility of euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

The patient is not sure

The patient does not want to answer this question

Answer if you are a doctor treating palliative patients. **How often do you treat palliative patients?**

All my patients are palliative patients

Sometimes I treat palliative patients

Answer if you are a doctor treating palliative patients. **How is medical care for palliative patients organized (in particular, pain relief)?**

Medical care meets all the needs of patients, analgesia is adequate to the needs

Medical care is unsatisfactory, patients do not have adequate analgesia

Answer if you are a doctor treating palliative patients.

Have palliative patients asked you for euthanasia ?

Yes

No

Answer if you are a doctor treating palliative patients. **Have relatives (guardians) of palliative patients asked you for euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a nurse who treats palliative patients. **How is medical care for palliative patients organized (in particular, pain relief)?**

Medical care meets all the needs of patients, analgesia is adequate to the needs

Medical care is unsatisfactory, patients do not have adequate analgesia

*Mandatory questions

Answer if you are a nurse who treats palliative patients. **Have palliative patients or their relatives (caregivers) told you about suicidal thoughts or attempts?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a nurse who treats palliative patients. **Have palliative patients asked you for euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a nurse who treats palliative patients. **Have relatives (guardians) of palliative patients asked you for euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a social worker who provides services to palliative patients (caregiver). **How is medical care for palliative patients and their social support organized?**

Medical care and their social support meet all the needs of patients

Medical care and their social support are insufficient

Answer if you are a social worker who provides services to palliative patients (caregiver). **Have palliative patients or their relatives (caregivers) told you about suicidal thoughts or attempts?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a social worker who provides services to palliative patients (caregiver). **Have palliative patients asked you about the possibility of euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a social worker who provides services to palliative patients (caregiver). **Have relatives (guardians) of palliative patients asked you about the possibility of euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a priest who provides spiritual support to palliative patients. **How is medical care for palliative patients and their spiritual support organized?**

Medical care and their spiritual support meet all the needs of patients

Medical care and their spiritual support are insufficient

*Mandatory questions

Answer if you are a priest who provides spiritual support to palliative patients.

Have palliative patients asked you about the possibility of euthanasia ? If so, what advice did you give?

Yes, but I advised not to fulfill it (not to strive)

Yes, but in Ukraine it is not possible by law

No

Answer if you are a priest who provides spiritual support to palliative patients.

Have relatives (guardians) of palliative patients asked you about the possibility of euthanasia ? If so, what advice did you give?

Yes, but I advised not to fulfill it (not to strive)

Yes, but in Ukraine it is not possible by law

No

Answer if you are a volunteer providing support to palliative patients (taking care of them). **How is medical care, social and spiritual support for palliative patients organized?**

Medical care, social and spiritual support meet all the needs of patients

Medical care, social and spiritual support are insufficient

Answer if you are a volunteer providing support to palliative patients (taking care of them). **Have palliative patients or their relatives (caregivers) told you about suicidal thoughts or attempts?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a volunteer providing support to palliative patients (taking care of them). **Have palliative patients asked you about the possibility of euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

Answer if you are a volunteer providing support to palliative patients (taking care of them). **Have relatives (guardians) of palliative patients asked you about the possibility of euthanasia ?**

Yes

No

QUESTIONS FOR EVERYONE**Should euthanasia be allowed in Ukraine?***

Yes

No

I don't have an answer

How should the legalization of euthanasia be discussed ?*

A wide public debate is needed

A professional discussion is needed (lawyers, deputies, doctors, other specialists providing assistance to palliative patients, palliative patients and their relatives)

This issue cannot be discussed publicly

Today is _____ (date)

*Mandatory questions